

Feasibility, safety, and reliability of exercise testing using the combined arm-leg (Cruiser) ergometer in subjects with a lower limb amputation

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Abstract

Physical fitness of patients with a lower limb amputation predicts their walking ability and may be improved by physical exercise and training. A maximal exercise test is recommended prior to training in order to determine cardiovascular risks and design exercise programs. A potentially suitable ergometer for maximal exercise testing in patients with a lower limb amputation is the combined arm-leg (Cruiser) ergometer. The aim of this study was to determine feasibility, safety, and reliability of (sub)maximal exercise testing on the Cruiser ergometer in subjects with a lower limb amputation. Subjects with a lower limb amputation performed 1 submaximal exercise test and 3 maximal exercise tests on the Cruiser ergometer. Feasibility was determined by examining whether key variables such as power output, heart rate and oxygen uptake were correctly and reliably measured, by determining whether a test was a maximal aerobic performance, by studying reasons for non-completion, and by measuring gross efficiency. Safety was analyzed by recording complications, electrocardiogram results, and blood pressure. Reliability was tested by comparing the results of the second and third maximal exercise test. Seventeen subjects completed the study. In general, the maximal Cruiser exercise test was feasible. Almost 75% of the subjects reached a maximal aerobic performance. The test was also safe because no complications occurred, although electrocardiogram and blood pressure could only be reliably recorded in most subjects just before and after the test. Reliability was good: Intraclass correlation was 0.84 for peak oxygen uptake. In conclusion the Cruiser ergometer is a feasible, safe, and reliable ergometer for measuring physical fitness of subjects with a lower limb amputation.

Keywords

exercise test, lower limb amputation, ergometer

Introduction

Patients who require a lower limb amputation (LLA) are often elderly and have a high prevalence of comorbidities, especially cardiovascular diseases (Remes et al. 2008). Before starting exercise training, a maximal exercise test is not only recommended for reasons of safety, especially with regard to cardiovascular risks, but also for developing individually tailored exercise programs. A potentially suitable ergometer for maximal exercise testing in patients with a lower limb amputation is the combined arm-leg (Cruiser) ergometer. Previous research has demonstrated that the Cruiser ergometer is a valid, reliable, and safe instrument for measuring the physical fitness of healthy volunteers (Simmelink et al. 2009). The aims of the current study are 1) to explore the feasibility of the Cruiser ergometer in maximal exercise testing in subjects with a LLA, 2) to evaluate the safety of the Cruiser ergometer, and 3) to study the test-retest reliability of a repeated maximal exercise test on the Cruiser ergometer.

Methods

Subjects with LLA performed one submaximal exercise test and three maximal exercise tests on the Cruiser ergometer. Feasibility was studied by examining whether key variables such as heart rate and oxygen uptake (VO_2) were correctly and confidently measured. The reasons for non-completion were studied. A 10-point Borg scale at peak load for dyspnea and for arm and leg muscle fatigue was assessed to determine the impact of the test. The maximal aerobic performance was evaluated for each test. The GE of movement during the submaximal period of was calculated and compared to previous research of Simmelink et. al (2015, 2016) in healthy volunteers. Safety was analyzed by recording complications and by registration of electrocardiogram (ECG) and blood pressure. Reliability of the second and third maximal exercise tests was assessed by means of paired t-tests, the one-way random effect model and single measure-intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC), and Bland-Altman plots. Level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1. The Cruiser ergometer

Results

Seventeen subjects (14 male and 3 female), out of twenty-one preselected subjects, completed the study. In general, the maximal Cruiser exercise test was feasible. Almost three quarters indeed reached maximal performance. The test was safe: no complications occurred, although

ECG and blood pressure could only be confidently registered in most subjects just before and after the test. The ICCs are presented in Table 1. It is advocated that an ICC of > 0.75 indicates good agreement. This means there is a good agreement for the outcome measures VO₂peak and PO_{peak} between tests 2 and 3.

Table 1: ICC of the second and third test for the peak oxygen uptake (VO₂), heart rate (HR) and power output (PO)

	ICC (single measure)	95% CI
VO ₂ , l/min	0.84	0.61 – 0.94
HR, 1/min	0.68	0.32 – 0.87
PO, W	0.91	0.77 – 0.97

Conclusion and discussion

In this study, feasibility, safety, and reliability of exercise testing on the combined arm-leg Cruiser ergometer were evaluated in subjects with a LLA. The test procedure was feasible because almost all subjects were able to perform the combined arm-leg movement and managed to reach adequate symptom scores. Furthermore, a large majority of subjects reached a maximal aerobic performance and most variables of interest could be measured appropriately. The test procedure was safe and ECGs could be reliably recorded in most cases. Approximately 20% of ECG recordings were severely influenced by muscle activity of arms and thorax. In addition, blood pressure could not be measured during the tests on the upper arm or on the wrist. Finally, the test-retest reliability was good.

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